

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Genetic composition of IR rice varieties

W. R. Coffman, plant breeder, and T. R. Hargrove, associate editor, International Rice Research Institute

Forces acting over the last two decades have clearly eroded the genetic diversity of cultivated rice varieties. It seems appropriate to assess the situation and consider whether and how future developments might influence genetic diversity. This is the first of several articles that will trace the origin of

modern varieties in major rice-growing countries.

Several countries have directly released the IR varieties — beginning with IR8 — and most national programs have used them heavily in crosses. A careful examination of the origin of the 15 IR varieties that have been named (including 4 named by the Philippines) reveals that 11 parents were utilized in their development. The 11 parents are traceable to 18 original varieties from 8 countries (Fig. 1).

Figure 2 traces the series of crosses from which the IR varieties were selected, emphasizing the maternal progenitors. All 15 trace back to the same maternal parent, Cina (formerly known as Tjina), from China via Indonesia. Thus, components of their cytoplasm would be similar.

This situation, while posing no immediate practical problem, is of sufficient concern to demand a prompt broadening of the maternal genetic base of modern rices.

1. The derivation of IR varieties.

